

1 **DNMT3B controls expression of BRD3/4.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Layered epigenetic control has remained difficult to decipher. We describe here control of BRD3 and
8 BRD4 by the DNA methyltransferase *DNMT3B*.

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10 Citations

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